

**NARRATIVE (RE/DE)CONSTRUCTION OF MEMORY
IN MARINA LEWYCKA'S NOVEL *A SHORT HISTORY
OF TRACTORS IN UKRAINIAN***

Lunyova T. (York, UK & Poltava, Ukraine)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7022-0821>

ABSTRACT. This study looks into memory construction, reconstruction and deconstruction within the narrative of Marina Lewycka's novel *A Short History of Tractors in Ukrainian*. The research follows cognitive poetic approach to narrative analysis. It focuses on revealing the representation of the phenomenon of memory in the novel and discussing how remembering is problematised in it. The results of the study demonstrate that metaphorical representation of memory as some material substance that can be found in some space pertains to the characters' understanding of how memory works while a more subtle representation of relational nature of memory is characteristic of the description of characters' deliberations and actions in the novel. The novel problematises the discrepancy between wishes for idealised past and real history, the achievability of constructing a complete narrative of the past, the benefits of knowing terrible stories from the past, the veracity of personal memories, the potential for ideological underpinnings of narratives about past events, the influence of the cherished memories on the perception of the current situation, and willingness/ reluctance to know and remember the history of one's country. The research also opens up an avenue for the further study of the role of memory in creating the dynamic tension between immigrants' preserving national identity and integrating into a new society as this is described in the novel.

KEYWORDS: memory, narrative, Ukraine, history, personal story, remembering, forgetting, telling, silencing.

Marina Lewycka's debut novel *A Short History of Tractors in Ukrainian* is written as a narration of the second-generation Ukrainian immigrant to the UK who

tells a story of the turbulence in her family brought about by her elderly father's marriage to a much younger Ukrainian woman desperately wishing to emigrate to the UK. The book was both awarded several literary prizes (Weretiuk, 2016, p. 154) and subjected to criticism (Kurkov, 2005). Memories play an important role in the unfolding of the story. As Natalie Watson succinctly put it: «This is a story about remembering, telling and about that which cannot be told and is best left unsaid» (2006, p. 238).

The narrator, a sociology university lecturer Nadezhda looks back trying to understand how the events in the past shaped her as a personality and her relationships with the father and older sister. Nadezhda finds out that there often exist two versions of the same event. She also becomes acutely aware of the many gaps in her family story as she knows it. At times, Nadezhda gets an answer from her older sister or her father, and some of these answers undermine her assumptions of what her family story was like. However, more often she faces the refusal of her family members to discuss past which is too painful for them. Besides, Nadezhda realises that it is hard to distinguish her own memories and stories told by her close relatives: «... *the harder I try to remember, the more I get confused about **which are memories and which are stories***» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 48). Nadezhda's father, a retired engineer with the poetic soul Nikolai Mayevskyj reminisces about beautiful *Ukraina* «*Such a landscape – it would make anyone an artist*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 26) and embarks on writing «*his great work: A short history of tractors in Ukrainian*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 58) which covers many turbulent events in Ukraine so that the readers of it «*will learn something about the history of our beloved motherland*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 80). Thus, as the narrative in the novel progresses, personal and collective memories are constructed, reconstructed and deconstructed.

The aim of this research is twofold: to reveal how the phenomenon of memory is represented and to determine how remembering is problematised in the novel.

The research is done within the cognitive poetic paradigm and builds upon the methodologies of cognitive poetic analysis of narratives.

The novel opens with a metaphoric representation of memory as material substance: «*She [Valentina] exploded into our lives like a fluffy pink grenade, churning up the murky water, bringing to the surface a sludge of sloughed-off memories*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 1). Such a conceptualisation of memory as some material objects that can be thrown away or retrieved is repeated throughout the novel, e.g.: «*I sit on the bench under the wild cherry tree in the cemetery and sort through my memories...*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 48), «*And I am dragged up into the dustbag of the past, full of clotted greying memories, where everything is formless, indistinct, lumpy with obscure gobs of matter shrouded in ancient dust...*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 90).

This metaphoric conceptualisation of memory corresponds to “accounts of memory as a storehouse” (Toolan, 2016, p. 191) which are typical of description of memory phenomena in natural language (Roediger, 1980). However, recent studies into the nature of memory suggest that metaphorical model of memory as a storage place is likely not to cover the true nature of memory. Thus, Michael Toolan, building upon Roy Harris’ description of memory as «the creative construction of a schema for integrating the past with the present» (Harris, 1997, as cited in Toolan, 2016, p. 192), proposes to «think of memories as more like relationships» (Toolan, 2016, p. 192). According to Toolan, it might be more productive to conceive of memory as «a network of experiences some of which, as occasion requires, we may be able selectively to bring to mind in coordinating present or future activity» (2016, p. 192–193). It is very interesting to observe that the novel *A Short History of Tractors in Ukrainian* captures the relational nature of memories and offers a more subtle representation of memory as a relationship between events in the past and the present, e.g.: «*And yet when I was a child my father made me such wonderful gifts. [...] I remember these gifts with wonder. [...] He always really likes presents, even though he says he doesn't*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 108–109). This quote from the novel renders narrator’s memories of the wonderful gifts she got from her father in her childhood. These memories were triggered by approaching Christmas. As Nadezhda was recalling getting those presents with many details (e.g., «*There were model aeroplanes made*

from balsa wood and powered with rubber band – all the street turned out to watch them fly» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 109)), she was also considering her feelings towards her father and how they had changed («*It is so long since I remembered the things I once loved about my father»* (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 109)). Besides, she took some actions based on her memories as her choice of the Christmas gift for her father was clearly influenced by her memories of his gifts for her: «*We get my father some chocolates and a book about aeroplanes»* (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 109).

In the novel, metaphoric representation of memory as some material objects pertains to the characters, in particular to the narrator (as the quotes above demonstrate) and to the narrator's sister Vera, e.g.: «*The past is filthy. It's like a sewer. You shouldn't play there. Leave it alone. Forget it»* (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 185). Representation of memory as a relationship between events in the past and the present evolves mainly as narrative construction in the novel. It helps to provide a deeper insight into the motives and actions of the characters. In this respect, it appears that Kurkov's harsh criticism of the characters of Ukrainians in the novel as «caricatures» (2005) is not well-grounded. Marina Lewycka does reach to the nuances of her characters' inner life through representing memory as a relational phenomenon.

Remembering and sharing memories via telling stories is presented in the novel as problematic in several aspects. Importantly, the novel reveals that it might be very uneasy for a person to reconcile the desire for having an idealised family past and the real family story. This challenge is depicted in the novel as the understanding the narrator Nadezhda managed to achieve and accept when she acknowledged that her wish to see her parents as characters of heroic-romantic story did not square with real life: «*When I was young, I wanted my father to be a hero. I was ashamed of his young graveyard desertion, his flight to Germany. I wanted my mother to be a romantic heroine. I wanted their story to be one of bravery and love. Now as an adult I see that they were not heroic. They survived, that's all»* (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 311). This «more nuanced view of her family story, in which her mother and father are normal people» (Fielding, 2011, p. 205) comes as a result of much effort on the side of Nadezhda to learn and accept her parents' past.

The very process of constructing a complete narrative that has no gaps to remember the past is presented as a difficult task. It cost Nadezhda a lot of efforts to discover missing pieces of her family story. Many of the conversations in the novel are Nadezhda's pleas to her father or older sister to tell her about the past and their refusal to do so. Nadezhda's pleas often remain unsuccessful as her relatives choose silencing themselves not to share traumatic experience, e.g.: «*'What happened with Vera and the cigarettes?'* / *There is a long silence.* / *'Can't remember'*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 91).

The novel raises the issue of the expediency of knowing harrowing stories from the past as the characters often express doubts that such knowledge could do any good, e.g.: «*'Pappa said something happened to you in the camp at Drachensee. Something about cigarettes. Can you remember?'* / *'Of course I can remember.'* *I wait for her to continue, and after a while she says. 'There are some things it's better not to know, Nadia'*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 268). Both Nadezhda's father and older sister for a long time refuse to tell her what happened to them and the Mother in German labour camp during the Second World War. Since the novel for a long time leaves this event «as an indescribable horror» not fleshed out (Fielding, 2011, p. 212), a strong emotional tension is created.

The novel also problematises veracity of personal memories which on the narrative level is represented as correcting the story told by one character by another, e.g.: «*'No, no,' says Vera. 'It didn't happen like that. They were plums, not cherries. And it was the NKVD that caught him, not the Germans'*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 237).

Besides, the novel demonstrates that telling a story might be motivated by an ideological reason and thus the story might become an argument rather than an account of events, e.g., «*'Who pulled it down?'* / *'The communists of course.'* / *Ha! So there is a subtext to this romantic story*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 64).

The novel also shows that cherished memories of the past can become obstacles to adequate perception of current reality. The narrator's father believes that his memory of Ukraine is still true to life, which is not the case, e.g.: «*Papa, Ukraine isn't like you*

remember it. It's different now» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 27). The discrepancy between Nikolai Mayevskyj's idealised memories and harsh contemporary realities is revealed in the novel with the help of the humour (Weretiuk, 2016, p. 161).

Last but not least, the novel exposes the refusal of some to learn the history of their country and thus partake in preserving the collective memory. Valentina, Nikolai Mayevskyj's second Ukrainian young wife aspiring to build a new life in the UK, does not know about Ukraine's history and never agrees to listen to his book which covers a lot of tragic events in Ukrainian history, e.g., «*'Clearly this Valentina, she is of quite different generation. She knows nothing of history, even less about recent past'*» (Lewycka, 2005/2007, p. 170).

Overall, Marina Lewycka's novel *A Short History of Tractors in Ukrainian* blends collective history and personal stories into a dynamic narrative in which memories are constructed, reconstructed, and deconstructed through the acts of focused remembering, deliberate attempts at forgetting, willing or reluctant telling, as well as silencing. The novel «illustrates that not only is the personal political, but the political is eminently personal, that the grand narratives of the ordering and re-ordering of the world ultimately break down into the stories of women, men and children who endeavour to survive» (Watson, 2006, p. 238). In doing so the novel also delves into the processes of preserving Ukrainian identity (Weretiuk, 2016) and assimilating to the British society (Fielding, 2011). It would be of interest to further investigate how narrative representations of memory in the novel contribute to presenting the dynamics of keeping national heritage and integrating into the culture of the country of immigration.

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